

Geophysics-based landslide zonation explains spatial variability in tree-ring growth disturbances

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ABSTRACT

Complex landslides contain internally heterogeneous zones that may respond differently to reactivation, complicating tree-ring based chronologies of slope activity. This study combines dendrogeomorphological analysis with electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) to test whether geophysics-based zonation could explain the spatial variability of tree-ring disturbances within a large complex landslide. ERT profiles and geomorphological mapping delineated three mechanically distinct zones: a downslope shallow-landslide sector (*S zone*), a moisture-rich gap infilled by weakly consolidated material (*G zone*), and an adjacent compact block with tension cracks (*B zone*). In total, 200 Norway spruce (*Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst) were analysed for reaction wood (RW) and abrupt growth suppression (GS). RW intensity was quantified for each affected ring and GS classified by relative ring-width reduction.

RW clearly dominates across the landslide. The *S zone* shows the highest stem inclinations and RW intensities, indicating enhanced shallow deformation, whereas RW duration is similar among zones. GS occurs everywhere but is proportionally most frequent in the *B zone*. Correlation analyses show that in the *S* and *G zones*, RW intensity and duration relate significantly to stem inclination, while no significant relationships appear in the *B zone*.

These results demonstrate that internal landslide heterogeneity, as delineated by ERT, is reflected in tree-ring responses. Geophysics-based zonation offers an effective framework for interpreting growth disturbances and improves dendrogeomorphic reconstructions of complex slope movements.

1. Introduction

Dendrogeomorphology is one of the most precise and widely used methods for dating landslides (Alestalo, 1971; Stoffel and Bollschweiler, 2008; Corona et al., 2014). Individual trees can live for several centuries, and tree rings provide annual to sub-annual resolution, allowing the development of long, high-resolution chronologies of slope activity (Šilhán et al., 2012). Landslide-induced deformation typically produces growth disturbances, most notably (i) reaction wood (RW), formed when stems are tilted or bent (Westing, 1965), and (ii) abrupt growth suppressions (GS), resulting from root damage, uprooting, or partial burial that inhibits physiological function (Stoffel and Bollschweiler, 2009; Šilhán, 2021). Eccentric growth patterns can further refine the timing and direction of movement (Braam et al., 1987; Wistuba et al., 2013). By cross-dating these signals across multiple trees in combination with their position, it is possible to reconstruct both the timing and spatial extent of past landslides with high accuracy (Stefanini, 2004;

Šilhán, 2020). Such reconstructions are essential for understanding long-term slope dynamics in areas lacking instrumental or documentary records (Lopez Saez et al., 2012).

However, dendrogeomorphic analysis of large, complex landslides remains challenging. These slopes rarely behave as single coherent units but instead consist of multiple kinematic zones, such as blocks, lobes, levees or tension cracks, each with distinct depth of shear surfaces, movement mechanisms, and sensitivities to external triggers (Corominas and Moya, 1999; Fantucci and Sorriso-Valvo, 1999). When tree-ring data from all zones are aggregated into a single chronology, local signals may be blurred or lost, and spurious peaks may emerge from the overlap of unrelated events (Šilhán et al., 2019b). This noise can obscure the true geomorphic signal, a problem evident even in smaller landslides with distinct source, transport, and accumulation zones. Šilhán et al. (2022) showed that more than a quarter of event years in a combined chronology were false positives, while actual failures recorded in specific zones were omitted. Their findings underscore the importance of

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zoning to reduce signal contamination and enhance the accuracy of dendrogeomorphic reconstructions.

Zonation involves subdividing a complex landslide into morphologically or structurally homogeneous sectors and producing separate chronologies for each. This process relies on detailed geomorphological mapping, ideally supported by geophysical surveys (Šilhán et al., 2022). Geophysical methods help reveal subsurface features such as internal stratigraphy, slip surfaces, or water-saturated zones (not detectable at the surface) and help define homogeneous landslide units (McCann and Forster, 1990; Jongmans and Garambois, 2007). Among these, electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) is particularly effective in identifying differences in bedrock conditions and moisture regimes (Schrott and Sass, 2008). ERT data complement surface mapping by confirming which slope sectors are underlain by colluvium, intact bedrock, or clay-rich layers likely to enhance movement. Integrating ERT with dendrogeomorphic analysis allows for more precise delineation of homogeneous zones and improves interpretation of growth disturbances in trees induced by specific landslide movements or character of landslide material. In the study of a complex landslide by Šilhán et al. (2019b), this integrated approach produced a clearer and more internally consistent chronology, revealing distinct activity patterns among zones. A key finding for the present study was that the intensity of growth disturbances varied significantly between zones, and some variability persisted even within seemingly homogeneous units—emphasising the need for fine-scale analysis (Šilhán et al., 2022).

Even when landslides are divided into homogeneous zones, internal variability within these units can still affect the interpretation of tree-ring responses. While such zones may appear uniform at the surface, geophysical investigations often reveal structural heterogeneities, such as subsurface shear zones, material contrasts, or moisture gradients (Perrone et al., 2014). Consequently, trees within the same zone may display markedly different responses to slope deformation. These differences reflect not only local deformation characteristics but also ecological variables, including species-specific sensitivity, rooting depth, soil properties, and microtopographic variation (Falco et al., 2019). Accurate reconstruction of landslide histories thus requires attention to both geophysical and ecological variability, even within zones classified as homogeneous.

Ślowik-Opoka (2020) showed that irregular annual growth increments in spruces positioned on different slope aspects correlated with erosive events affecting tree development. This highlights how slope gradient and movement can influence individual tree responses, leading to high intra-zone variability. Similarly, Falco et al. (2019) found that vegetation distribution is strongly governed by microtopography and soil moisture, with trees in wetter microsites maintaining stable growth and those in drier, unstable areas showing reduced or erratic growth patterns. Further, Watlet et al. (2024) used ERT to demonstrate that moisture accumulation patterns strongly correlate with slope movement, confirming that resistivity-based moisture maps can indicate zones vulnerable to deformation. These insights support the value of combining dendrogeomorphic and geophysical approaches to better understand and interpret tree responses on unstable slopes.

In light of these considerations, this study integrates dendrogeomorphic analysis with ERT-based geophysical data to investigate a large complex landslide. The dendrogeomorphic analysis focuses on the two primary tree responses to slope movement: reaction wood (RW) and abrupt growth suppression (GS). By analysing these indicators, we aim to assess whether trees in different zones preferentially exhibit one type of response, and whether this variation is linked to substrate conditions. The central research question is whether differences in tree responses correspond to differences in material properties, e.g., shallow, unconsolidated substrates versus deeper bedrock or compact materials. Integrating ERT with dendrogeomorphology enables a more detailed interpretation of these relationships.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the variability of tree responses across different zones within a single complex landslide

system. This aim is addressed through three sub-objectives: (i) to assess how internal material heterogeneity influences the nature of growth disturbances, (ii) to determine whether trees in different zones tend to exhibit distinct response types (RW or GS), and (iii) to evaluate the significance of response differences across zones. By combining dendrogeomorphology with geophysical imaging, we aim to reduce uncertainties arising from internal slope complexity and enhance the reliability of landslide chronologies.

2. Study area

The study was conducted at the same location investigated by Šilhán et al. (2019b), which features a complex slope deformation previously analysed using dendrogeomorphological methods. The site was revisited in this research due to a distinct scientific objective compared to the earlier study. It represents the nearest suitable complex slope deformation that meets all the key criteria for dendrogeomorphic analysis, including well-preserved forest cover, clear morphological features, and accessible terrain. While the original study focused on the classic spatial-temporal reconstruction of landslide movements, this study focuses on a completely different aspect, i.e., the dependence of the nature of growth disturbances on the internal properties of individual landslide zones. For this purpose, additional trees were sampled in the area that had already been studied in the past.

The study site is situated in the eastern part of the Vsetínské vrchy highlands (Outer Western Carpathians, Czech Republic) (Fig. 1A). This region lies at the denudation front of the Magura nappe, where strongly folded and lithological variable layers of flysch rocks are exposed. The flysch complex consists primarily of alternating beds of siltstones, sandstones, and claystones, whose differing resistance to weathering and erosion gives rise to characteristic structural relief (Demek and Mackovčín, 2006). A prominent geological feature of the area is a diagonal fault aligned with the Bystrická River valley, which disrupts the original sedimentary and tectonic fabric and significantly influences the present-day geomorphology and slope stability. Structural landforms have developed under the combined effects of erosion and denudation, and the area also features boulder flows and prominent sandstone cliffs, shaped by tectonic discontinuities and selective weathering processes (Baroň et al., 2004).

The region is characterized by a high concentration of slope deformations of various types, with a spatial density considered unique within Central Europe (Kirchner and Krejčí, 1998; Šilhán et al., 2018). These slope instabilities are often structurally controlled, typically occurring along bedding planes or within zones of weakness associated with tectonic disruptions of the rock mass (Klimeš, 2008). According to (Pánek et al., 2010), deep weathering in claystone-rich zones has significantly contributed to slope instability, with the weathered mantle above the bedrock reaching depths of several metres.

The forest stands in the area are predominantly composed of Norway spruce (*Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst.) and European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.), which have recolonised the slopes since the cessation of intensive grazing in the late 19th century (Adam et al., 2015). Minor components of the forest community include silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.), sycamore maple (*Acer pseudoplatanus* L.), European larch (*Larix decidua* Mill.), and silver birch (*Betula pendula* L.).

The investigated landslide area (centred at 49.383°N, 18.233°E) is classified as a complex landslide (Cruden and Varnes, 1996), comprising a variety of partial slope deformations. The site covers approximately 9 ha and spans an elevation range of 140 m, from 640 to 780 m a.s.l (Fig. 1C). The upper slope is dominated by large landslide blocks composed of calcareous claystones and glauconitic sandstones. The distal parts of these blocks are disrupted by tension cracks, while the lower slope features shallow landslides with undulating surfaces, developed in weathered colluvial material. These shallow failures occur at the toe of the larger blocks and in lower slope positions. The western margin of the site is defined by pronounced debris flow paths, and

Fig. 1. Location of the studied area and its geomorphology. A – locations within the Czech Republic, B – location within the region and description of the place (a – mountain peaks, b – roads and paths, c – streams, d – buildings, e – contour line), C – geomorphic scheme of the landslide area (1 – source scarp of debris flow, 2 – main scarp, 3 – tension cracks, 4 – lateral debris flow levee, 5 – debris flow cone, 6 – minor step, 7 – frontal lobe, 8 – landslide block, 9 – contour line, 10 – ERT profile, 11 – trees in G zone, 12 – trees in B zone, 13 – trees in S zone, 14 – location of photos from Fig. 2).

several smaller landslide blocks are situated upslope of the debris source zone. Importantly, tourist facilities are located only tens of metres upslope from the main escarpment, indicating a potential hazard to infrastructure (Fig. 1B). The site is predominantly forested with *P. abies*, with *F. sylvatica* occupying several smaller patches, particularly in the south-eastern sector. A significant proportion of the trees display signs of ongoing slope deformation, including leaning or curved trunks and exposed roots, especially in areas near thrust cracks and along the main scarp.

3. Methods

3.1. Geomorphological mapping and geophysical sounding

A key component of this study was the subdivision of the complex landslide into internally homogeneous zones. Zonation was based on detailed geomorphological mapping (ca 1:500), a LiDAR-derived digital elevation model (DEM), and electrical resistivity tomography sounding (ERT). Geomorphological mapping at a scale of 1:500 enabled the identification of surface landforms, while the DEM helped delineate surface boundaries between zones. This approach allowed the identification of three main components of the landslide: the main block, lower block, and shallow landslide, following the classification by Šilhán et al. (2019b). The present study focused in greater detail on the *main block* (Fig. 1).

A total of three ERT surveys were conducted along three profiles. The first profile was 70 m long with an electrode spacing of 2 m to allow for higher-resolution imaging of internal structures. The Wenner-Schlumberger array was used as it offers a good balance for detecting both vertical and horizontal features (Kearey et al., 2002; Milsom, 2003; Schrott and Sass, 2008). The second profile, located 45 m from the first and measuring 76 m in length, used the same configuration. The third profile was 300 m long with a 5 m electrode spacing, also employing the Wenner-Schlumberger array. Inversion modelling was performed in the specialized software Res2DInv (Loke and Barker, 1996). The layout of the profiles was deliberately selected to capture the internal structure of the entire landslide, with a particular focus on the *main block*. Although

profile C–C' crosses forested area, trees located along this profile were not included in the dendrogeomorphic analysis. Tree sampling was intentionally restricted to predefined landslide zones (S, G and B), where trees could be reliably attributed to distinct deformation regimes. The purpose of profile C–C' was primarily to characterize the overall subsurface structure of the entire landslide rather than to directly link geophysical data to individual trees along the profile.

The integration of the three methods enabled the delineation of three distinct zones within the complex landslide. Specifically, one zone was identified in the shallow landslide sector and two within the main block (Fig. 4B). The shallow landslide area was designated as the *S zone*. The remaining two zones, located within the main block, were defined based on the nature of its movement—characterized by subsidence with slight rotational displacement, as described by Šilhán et al. (2019b). These were named the *G zone* and *B zone*, referring respectively to a structural gap filled with unconsolidated material (*G zone*) and a displaced compact block (*B zone*) (Fig. 2A, B; Fig. 4A). The decision to distinguish these zones was based on the expectation that each would impose different types and intensities of mechanical stress on trees due to varying subsurface conditions and movement dynamics. Accordingly, tree responses were hypothesized to differ between zones. Subsequent dendrogeomorphic analyses were therefore conducted separately for each zone to test whether the observed growth disturbances reflect these differences in slope behaviour and internal structure.

3.2. Dendrogeomorphic approach

For the dendrogeomorphic analysis, increment cores were extracted using a Pressler increment borer (length: 40 cm, diameter: approx. 0.5 cm). Sampling was carried out in April and May 2024. In total, samples were collected from 202 trees of *P. abies*. Two cores were taken from each tree—one from the downslope side and the other from the opposite side—always at the point of maximum trunk bending. For each tree, trunk tilt was measured using an inclinometer, rounded to the nearest whole degree, and the position was recorded using a GNSS device.

The increment cores were processed following standard procedures as described by Bräker (2002) or Stoffel and Bollschweiler (2008).

Fig. 2. Photos from the studied area. A – view from the crown of landslide to G and B zone, B – side view on the main block (G and B zone), C – side view on the one part of shallow landslide zone (S zone), D – tension crack near the S zone.

Samples were air-dried and mounted on wooden holders. They were then sanded using 150, 250, and 2000 grit sandpapers to enhance annual ring visibility. All samples were scanned using an EPSON Expression 12,000 XL scanner at 2400 DPI resolution. Tree-ring width measurement and initial dating were performed using Coorecorder software (Maxwell and Larsson, 2021). Cross-dating with the reference chronology was conducted in CDendro (Maxwell and Larsson, 2021), and the quality of cross-dating was verified in COFECHA (Holmes, 1983). The reference chronology used for cross-dating and for the identification of locally induced growth disturbances was constructed from a subset of 30 trees that showed no visible signs of disturbance. All remaining samples were subsequently compared against this chronology to isolate geomorphically induced signals from those related to regional climatic variability. Following cross-dating, the samples were assigned to one of three groups based on their location within the landslide: S zone, G zone, or B zone. Growth disturbances (reaction wood or growth suppression) were then evaluated separately within each zone.

To enable consistent quantification and subsequent analysis, the presence and intensity of reaction wood (RW) were assessed using a visual estimation method. Each tree ring in which RW was detected was

divided into five equal segments, with each segment representing 20% of the total ring width (see Fig. 3). Based on how many of these segments were occupied by RW, the intensity of RW in a given ring was expressed as a percentage interval (e.g., if RW covered three segments, the intensity was recorded as 40–60%). For statistical analysis, the midpoint of each interval was used as a representative value (e.g., 30% for the 20–40% interval). This approach allowed for a semi-quantitative but reproducible assessment of RW intensity across all samples. Three key parameters were derived from this evaluation: (i) the mean RW intensity across all tree rings containing RW in each sample, (ii) the RW intensity in the second tree ring following the onset of RW formation, and (iii) the duration of RW expression, measured as the number of consecutive years in which RW was present. This procedure provided a basis for comparing RW expression across the different landslide zones.

To analyse abrupt growth suppressions (GS), we followed the method proposed by Schweingruber et al. (1990). This approach is based on comparing the width of a given tree ring with the average width of the four preceding rings. The resulting ratio is expressed as a percentage and used to classify into one of three categories: slight, moderate, or strong (see Fig. 3). A reduction of $\geq 40\%$ and $< 55\%$

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of the classification of reaction wood (RW) and abrupt growth suppression (GS). The upper panel shows the visual estimation of RW intensity based on five equal 20% segments of each ring, while the lower panel displays the GS intensity classes derived from percent reduction in ring width relative to the preceding four-year mean.

relative to the preceding four-year mean was classified as slight. A reduction between $\geq 55\%$ and $< 70\%$ was considered moderate, while a reduction of $\geq 70\%$ and $< 100\%$ was classified as strong. To be considered a valid geomorphic signal, the suppression had to be absent from the reference chronology, thus excluding growth reductions caused by regional climatic factors. As with RW, the duration of GS was also assessed, defined as the number of consecutive years in which ring width remained visibly reduced.

In addition to the two disturbance types, a standard event–response index (I_t) was calculated to define a landslide event and express its magnitude as defined by (Shroder, 1978):

$$I_t = \frac{\sum R_t}{\sum N_t} \times 100\%$$

where R_t is the number of trees exhibiting a growth disturbance in year t , and N_t is the total number of living trees sampled for that year. Landslide events are typically identified when the I_t index exceeds a defined threshold based on sample size (Corona et al., 2014; Stoffel et al., 2013). In this study, the following thresholds were applied: (i) if the sample size was ≤ 20 , the threshold was set at 15%; (ii) for sample sizes between 21 and 50, the threshold was 10%; (iii) if the sample size exceeded 50, the threshold was set at 7.5%.

3.3. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2021). Prior to correlation analysis, all variables were tested for normality using the Shapiro–Wilk test. If the data were normally distributed, Pearson's correlation coefficient was used; otherwise, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was applied. Data distribution also determined the choice of statistical tests used to compare variables across the three zones. When normality was confirmed, one-way ANOVA was used; in cases of non-normal distribution, the non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis (K–W) test was applied. If ANOVA yielded a significant result, the Games–Howell post-hoc test was used to identify which pairs of zones differed significantly. In the case of a significant K–W test result, Dunn's post-hoc test was employed for pairwise comparisons. All statistical tests were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. All maps were produced in ArcGIS Pro version 3.2.2. (Esri, 2024) and subsequently edited in a graphic design program to enhance visual clarity and presentation quality.

4. Results

4.1. Landslide zones and inner structure

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) reveals clear internal contrasts between the landslide zones (Fig. 4). Profiles 1 and 2 image the upper part of the *main block*. The *G zone* displays consistently low resistivities ($\approx 7\text{--}50 \Omega\text{-m}$), indicative of unconsolidated, moisture-rich colluvium or disturbed material occupying a structural gap. In contrast, the *B zone* shows higher resistivity ($\approx 80\text{--}200+ \Omega\text{-m}$) indicating a more compact block. The ERT characteristics of the shallow-landslide sector (*S zone*) are derived from Profile 3, which images the entire slope. In this profile, resistivities drop downslope from the main block and remain low within the *S zone* ($\approx 14\text{--}30 \Omega\text{-m}$), consistent with saturated, clay-rich colluvial material and shallow, distributed deformation. Profile 3 also confirms the resistive body beneath the main block and a pronounced high-resistivity ridge beneath the mapped tension cracks, interpreted as a fault. Together, the three ERT profiles substantiate the zonation used for the dendrogeomorphic analysis by delineating mechanically distinct domains within the landslide.

4.2. Dendrogeomorphic data

We analysed 200 Norway spruce (*P. abies*) trees with ages from 28 to 60 years (mean 50.0 years, stdev = 9.6). By zone, the sample comprised 55 trees (*S zone*), 104 (*G zone*), and 41 (*B zone*), from which we identified 379 growth disturbances (GDs) in total – 319 reaction wood (RW) and 60 growth suppressions (GS). Per zone, GDs totals equal 114 (*S zone*), 206 (*G zone*) and 59 (*B zone*), with RW:GS breakdowns of 104:10, 172:34, and 43:16, respectively (Table 1). These findings indicate that RW is the dominant GD across the whole landslide ($\approx 84\%$ of all GDs), while GS forms a secondary component ($\approx 16\%$). Across the trees, stem inclination ranged from 0° to 8° with a mean of 0.8 (stdev = 1.3°). Mean inclination decreased from 1.5° in the *S zone* to 0.7° in the *G zone* and 0.3° in the *B zone* (Table 1).

Fig. 5 summarises disturbance occurrence. The proportion of trees with RW declines from *S zone* (91%) to *G zone* (72%) and *B zone* (66%), whereas GS affected 16%, 23% and 32% of trees in *S*, *G* and *B*, respectively. Considering disturbance counts, RW remains prevalent in every zone but its share decreases from *S zone* (91%) to *G* (83%) and *B* (73%).

Event–response (I_t) chronologies (Fig. 6) indicate episodic reactivation rather than sustained movement: the *S zone* shows peaks in the 1990s (esp. 1996 and 1997) and in 2002 and 2016, the *G zone* in the early 1970s and early 2000s, and the *B zone* in the early 1970s, 1984 and 2022.

4.3. Comparative analysis of RW/GS and stem inclination across landslide zones

Fig. 7 represents zone-specific distributions of RW and GS intensity and duration, as well as stem inclination, including the corresponding significance tests. Statistical comparisons demonstrate significant among-zone differences for RW and stem inclination, but not for GS. The mean RW intensity differs significantly among zones (one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.01$). Games-Howell post-hoc test indicates higher RW intensity values in *S zone* relative to *G* and *B zones*. The early response (RW intensity in the second tree-ring after onset) follows the same pattern (K–W test, $p < 0.01$; Dunn's post-hoc test). By contrast, the duration of RW (consecutive years with RW) shows no significant differences among zones (K–W test, $p = 0.16$). Neither intensity (K–W test, $p = 0.47$) nor duration of GS (K–W test, $p = 0.83$) varies among zones. Stem inclination differs markedly among zones (K–W test, $p < 0.01$), with higher inclinations in *S zone* than in *G* or *B zones*. Fig. 7 thus shows that the *S zone* combines stronger RW intensity with greater stem inclination, while RW duration and all GS metrics are consistent across zones. These results motivate the correlation analyses below (Fig. 8–9).

Fig. 4. ERT profiles used to delineate the three landslide zones. Profiles 1 and 2 (A) resolve internal contrasts within the main block, with low-resistivity unconsolidated infill in the *G zone* and higher-resistivity compact material in the *B zone*. Profile 3 (B) images the full slope, showing the transition from the main block to the shallow-landslide sector (*S zone*) and highlighting tension cracks and a resistive ridge interpreted as a fault.

Table 1
Number, ages and stem inclination of trees and number of growth disturbances in individual zones.

	Trees	Age				Stem inclination (°)				GD's	RW	GS
		Min	Max	Mean	St. dev.	Min	Max	Mean	St. dev.			
<i>S zone</i>	55	28	39	35.0	2.1	0	8	1.5	1.9	114	104	10
<i>G zone</i>	104	43	60	55.5	2.8	0	4	0.7	1.0	206	172	34
<i>B zone</i>	41	49	60	56.3	2.2	0	2	0.3	0.5	59	43	16
Total	200	28	60	50.0	9.6	0	8	0.8	1.3	379	319	60

For RW, several zone-specific associations are evident (Fig. 8). In the *S zone*, RW intensity shows a positive correlation with stem inclination (Spearman $\rho = 0.44$, $p < 0.01$) and RW duration correlates with stem inclination ($\rho = 0.52$, $p < 0.01$). In the *G zone*, RW intensity increases with duration ($\rho = 0.50$, $p < 0.01$) and duration relates positively to stem inclination ($\rho = 0.31$, $p < 0.01$). Other RW relationships are non-significant (e.g., all in *B zone*). For GS, correlations are generally non-significant (Fig. 9). Intensity vs. duration is weak, with a near-threshold association in *G zone* ($\rho = 0.39$, $p = 0.06$).

5. Discussion

The integrated analysis of tree-ring records and ERT imaging enables not only the reconstruction of landslide activity in time, but also the interpretation of how internal structural heterogeneity controls deformation processes and associated tree growth responses. ERT-derived

subsurface contrasts define distinct mechanical environments across the landslide, which systematically govern the dominant modes of tree growth disturbance. Tree-ring responses are not spatially uniform. They vary systematically across the *S*, *G* and *B zones* in line with the subsurface conditions derived from ERT. The dendrogeomorphic signal in the *S zone* contrasts with patterns commonly reported from shallow landslides, where GS typically prevails as the dominant response (Šilhán et al., 2022; Klimeš et al., 2024). In our case, however, RW clearly dominates both in the number of affected trees and in the total count of GDs (see Table 1). This deviation could be explained by the mechanical behaviour of the substrate, which—according to ERT results, field observations, and previous findings by Šilhán et al. (2019b)—is rich in clay particles, giving it higher cohesion and plasticity. Such conditions allow the shallow landslide to move as a coherent, plastically deforming block rather than as a fragmented mass that would cause extensive root damage and, consequently, GS formation. Although the depth and

Fig. 5. Proportions of trees with reaction wood (RW) and growth suppression (GS) in the S, G, and B zones. A – RW occurrence, B – GS occurrence, C – relative RW–GS contributions to total disturbances.

structure of root systems were not directly verified, the observed correlations between stem inclination and reaction wood (RW) parameters likely reflect cumulative mechanical tilting associated with slow, cohesive slope deformation. Previous studies have shown that macroscopic RW characteristics (e.g. intensity or duration) often correlate with stem inclination, but also emphasize that this relationship is influenced by multiple factors and should not be interpreted as a direct causal link (Šilhán, 2017a; Wiśniewská and Šilhán, 2022). It should be acknowledged that GS may also be influenced by external environmental stressors unrelated to landslide activity, such as insect outbreaks, drought, or air pollution, which can reduce annual growth even in the absence of mechanical root damage.

The *G zone* represents a domain characterized by unconsolidated, moisture-rich infill as inferred from ERT. Here, RW remains the predominant growth disturbance, though its relative proportion and intensity are lower than in the *S zone*, while GS becomes more frequent (Fig. 10). This mixed signal reflects the mechanical environment of the zone: intermittent decoupling and small-scale differential movement likely induce both stem tilting and episodic root stress. The observed

correlations between RW parameters (higher RW intensity associated with longer RW duration) and stem inclination (Fig. 8) are consistent with a deformation regime characterized by repeated, low-magnitude movements rather than a single abrupt tilting event. However, such relationships should be interpreted cautiously, as RW expression reflects cumulative mechanical effects and may be influenced by heterogeneous strain distribution within weak, partially saturated material.

Although in *B zone* present-day stem inclinations are the lowest among trees within the complex landslide, RW remains the dominant growth disturbance here as well. However, what distinguishes zone *B* from zones *S* and *G* is the higher occurrence of GS (Fig. 10). A plausible explanation is the location of trees along tension cracks mapped within the block and confirmed by ERT: trees growing near these cracks are susceptible to root damage caused by partial cutting off or drying out—conditions that lead to GS (Lopez-Saez et al., 2017; Šilhán, 2021). The absence of significant correlations (Figs. 8–9) is consistent with (i) the low sample size for GS and (ii) strong spatial heterogeneity of strain within the block, where tree responses depend on proximity to tension cracks (Šilhán et al., 2019a, 2019b). Taken together, these observations

Fig. 6. Event years detected by the I_t index in the S, G and B zones. Red bars mark event years exceeding the zone-specific threshold; grey bars represent non-event years; shaded area shows sample depth through time.

indicate a fracture-controlled disturbance regime in the B zone: RW likely records earlier tilting phases, whereas the most recent reactivation is expressed primarily as GS in trees affected by tension-crack dynamics. One of the causes may be the gradual development of a compact landslide block, which may have fragmented during the reconstruction period, thereby changing its effect on tree growth.

Previous dendrogeomorphological studies have typically reported contrasting tree-ring responses for shallow and rotational landslides, with GS often prevailing in shallow landslides due to frequent root damage, while RW is more commonly associated with rotational or slow-moving landslides (e.g. Stoffel and Bollschweiler, 2009; Šilhán, 2017b; Klimeš et al., 2024). In contrast, our results demonstrate that within a single complex landslide, both response types may coexist and dominate in different parts of the slope, depending on local mechanical conditions. The ERT-based zonation reveals that zones exhibiting shallow-slide behaviour, weakly consolidated infill, or compact blocks with tension cracks correspond to deformation regimes that produce tree-ring signals typically attributed to different landslide types. This highlights that treating complex landslides as internally homogeneous systems may obscure process-specific tree responses, whereas integrating geophysical zonation allows these contrasting mechanisms to be resolved within a single landslide body.

While the intensity of RW varies significantly across zones, the duration of RW remains very similar in all cases (Figs. 7A and 10). The combination of these findings confirms the assertion that RW intensity reflects the magnitude of mechanical stress, while RW duration is limited by internal regulatory limits of the gravitropic system and cambial kinetics (Timell, 1986; Coutand et al., 2007; Gardiner et al., 2014). In contrast, there are no significant differences across zones in the intensity or duration of GS (Fig. 7B and 10). This response is thus more spatially uniform in this case. As for tree damage, it is more episodic or locally concentrated. Reaction wood is thus the main signal carrier across all zones.

In addition to these interpretative aspects, it is important to acknowledge that the percentage-based assessment of RW intensity inevitably involves a degree of visual interpretation, and thus a potential observer-related bias. To minimize subjectivity, RW intensity was evaluated using a standardized segmentation approach applied consistently across all samples. Moreover, the analysis focuses on relative differences in RW intensity and duration among landslide zones rather than on absolute values. As a result, any residual uncertainty related to visual estimation is unlikely to affect the main conclusions regarding spatial contrasts in tree growth responses.

The I_t index (Fig. 6) shows episodic reactivation, which varies

Fig. 7. Boxplots showing between-zone differences: A – reaction wood intensity, its onset response, and duration; B – intensity and duration of growth suppression; C – stem inclination. Significant among-zone differences are indicated.

between zones. Importantly, separate analysis of zones avoids two known biases in overall chronologies for complex landslides: (i) underdetection of small, spatially limited reactivations and (ii) over-identification of years dominated by accelerated creep, with dispersed reactions pushing the I_t index above the threshold (Šilhán et al., 2022). The threshold was set with regard to the sample size as recommended by Corona et al. (2014), and the lower limit (7.5%) was set according to Šilhán (2016) due to a similar research design. Our approach thus reflects recent calls for the interpretation of the I_t index in individual zones separately. When interpreting the I_t index, however, it is necessary to keep in mind that the dendrological and calendar years are not the same period. When a partial landslide reactivates in the second half of the calendar year, the tree's response usually comes in the following year (Šilhán et al., 2019a). Similarly, the index may be overestimated, especially in S zone, due to the occurrence of shallow creep (Šilhán, 2017b).

The study faces several limitations. The most substantial is the uneven sample size among zones, a consequence of recent logging activities that reduced tree availability in the G and B zones. Increment cores were therefore collected only from trees that remained accessible. Although the overall number of sampled trees (200) is comparable to that used in previous dendrogeomorphological studies on complex landslides (e.g. Stefanini, 2004; Šilhán et al., 2019b, 2022; Zhang et al., 2019), this imbalance reduces statistical power in zones with fewer trees, particularly affecting analyses of less frequent growth disturbances such as GS. As a result, the absence of statistically significant differences or correlations in some GS-related parameters should be interpreted with caution, as it may partly reflect limited sample size rather than the absence of a geomorphic signal. In contrast, patterns consistently observed across multiple RW-related parameters and zones are less sensitive to sample-size effects and can therefore be considered more robust. The interpretation of spatial contrasts is further supported

by their systematic correspondence with the ERT-derived zonation. Additional constraints include the absence of excavation to directly verify subsurface conditions, and the relatively uniform age structure of the stand, which limits insights into responses of older trees. Future work could address these limitations by incorporating targeted root-zone investigations, sampling additional tree species for comparison, or repeating ERT surveys to monitor temporal changes in subsurface moisture dynamics.

However, this study also has several methodological strengths, most notably in its integrated approach. The combination of dendrogeomorphic approach with geophysical measurements provides a multidisciplinary perspective that enhances the interpretation of slope processes. The strength of the study, however, lies not only in the coupling of these two methods but also in the analytical treatment of RW. Unlike many dendrogeomorphic studies that assess RW intensity or duration using coarse categorical scales such as mild or pronounced (Šilhán, 2016; Stoffel and Bollschweiler, 2009), this work uses a percentage-based evaluation similar to Šilhán et al. (2019a).

By integrating geophysics with dendrogeomorphology, this study demonstrates that (i) areas with shallow landslides (S zone) that exhibit distinct RW, commonly accompanied by increased stem inclination reflecting ongoing slope deformation; (ii) weakly consolidated material (G zone) produces mixed RW and GS signals depending on local conditions; and (iii) GS occurrence increases in compact blocks (B zone) with tension cracks. Our findings therefore suggest that ERT-based zoning should be considered a highly desirable approach for complex landslides in order to separate areas with different mechanical behaviour before constructing a chronology. This would improve the design of monitoring and interpretation of future chronologies based on tree rings on complex slopes.

Fig. 8. Relationships between stem inclination and reaction wood (RW) parameters, shown separately for the S, G and B zones. Trend lines represent Spearman correlations; shaded areas denote 95% confidence intervals.

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the value of integrating dendrogeomorphic analysis with geophysical measurement to reveal internal heterogeneity and spatial variations in slope behaviour within a large complex landslide. ERT proved essential for delineating three mechanically distinct zones, enabling dendrogeomorphic signals to be interpreted in direct relation to subsurface conditions rather than merged into a single chronology.

Tree-ring evidence shows that deformation processes differ markedly

among these zones. In the shallow landslide sector (S zone), trees exhibit the strongest stem inclinations and the highest RW intensities, indicating enhanced kinematic activity. In contrast, the main block (G and B zones) displays more stable behaviour: the G zone records mixed RW–GS signals consistent with deformation in weakly consolidated infill, whereas the B zone shows the highest proportion of GS linked to root disturbance near tension cracks. Despite these contrasts, RW remains the dominant disturbance type across the entire landslide, while GS is spatially limited and largely associated with fracture-controlled processes.

These results demonstrate the diagnostic power of combining ERT

Fig. 9. Relationships between growth suppression (GS) parameters, shown separately for the S, G and B zones. Trend lines represent Spearman correlations; shaded areas denote 95% confidence intervals.

Fig. 10. Schematic synthesis of zone-specific subsurface conditions (ERT), stem deformation, and distribution of growth disturbances (RW, GS) across the G, B and S zones.

and dendrogeomorphic approach to identify internal variability in landslide behaviour. Zone-specific differences in both subsurface conditions and deformation styles translate directly into distinct patterns of tree growth disturbances. Such integrated approaches offer a more

precise basis for interpreting past activity, reduce noise in dendrogeomorphic chronologies, and improve the reliability of hazard assessments in complex slope systems. The methodological design further shows that refined quantification of RW intensity across all affected tree

rings provides additional sensitivity to spatial differences in mechanical loading—this approach could deserve wider attention in future studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Filip Schlesinger: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Karel Šilhán:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

[Tree ring data for analysis of RW and GS \(Original data\)](#) (Figshare)

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